

Quadrant Statistics

File: Annaxin 16032022.001
 Sample ID: Sample 1
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 16-Mar-22
 Gated Events: 9981
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 19, 22

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	731	7.32	7.31	3.59	2.00	491.60	373.30
UR	549	5.50	5.49	112.48	78.63	265.89	176.57
LL	5584	55.95	55.84	4.20	3.18	1.88	1.39
LR	3117	31.23	31.17	105.13	81.46	1.34	1.10

Quadrant Statistics

File: Annaxin 16032022.002
 Sample ID: Sample 2
 Tube: tube #2
 Acquisition Date: 16-Mar-22
 Gated Events: 9966
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 19, 22

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	808	8.11	8.08	4.86	2.61	303.49	218.45
UR	394	3.95	3.94	95.83	66.66	162.07	117.28
LL	6117	61.38	61.17	5.60	4.40	1.53	1.22
LR	2647	26.56	26.47	101.32	75.39	1.53	1.14

Quadrant Statistics

File: Annaxin 16032022.003
 Sample ID: Sample 3
 Tube: tube #3
 Acquisition Date: 16-Mar-22
 Gated Events: 5104
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 10

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 5115
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	607	11.89	11.87	2.98	2.13	197.14	154.18
UR	382	7.48	7.47	54.17	37.01	165.30	123.63
LL	3382	66.26	66.12	1.92	1.59	1.42	1.27
LR	733	14.36	14.33	69.65	41.28	1.09	1.04

Quadrant Statistics

File: Annaxin 16032022.004
 Sample ID: Sample 4
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 16-Mar-22
 Gated Events: 6818
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 10

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 6855
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	483	7.08	7.05	1.57	1.31	115.96	75.01
UR	457	6.70	6.67	94.95	74.02	93.31	57.33
LL	1596	23.41	23.28	2.72	2.22	1.32	1.15
LR	4282	62.80	62.47	59.11	45.85	1.12	1.04

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Quadrant Statistics

File: Annexin 07042022.001
 Sample ID: Sample 1
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 07-Apr-22
 Gated Events: 9997
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 10

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	201	2.01	2.01	2.01	1.54	93.98	69.95
UR	199	1.99	1.99	133.30	82.38	93.13	59.55
LL	9318	93.21	93.18	2.19	1.88	1.28	1.17
LR	279	2.79	2.79	165.52	78.80	1.65	1.32

Quadrant Statistics

File: Annexin 07042022.002
 Sample ID: Sample 2
 Tube: tube #2
 Acquisition Date: 07-Apr-22
 Gated Events: 9993
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 10

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	277	2.77	2.77	4.55	3.42	131.99	69.96
UR	672	6.72	6.72	104.24	62.98	141.17	89.50
LL	4362	43.65	43.62	5.06	4.41	2.13	1.63
LR	4682	46.85	46.82	85.82	50.93	1.57	1.26

Quadrant Statistics

File: Annexin 07042022.005
 Sample ID: Sample 5
 Tube: tube #2
 Acquisition Date: 07-Apr-22
 Gated Events: 9975
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 16, 15

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	1177	11.80	11.77	4.18	2.72	154.00	101.64
UR	512	5.13	5.12	75.75	52.60	187.89	120.78
LL	7494	75.13	74.94	4.32	3.46	3.12	2.33
LR	792	7.94	7.92	81.31	53.77	2.18	1.46

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Quadrant Statistics

File: Annexin 07042022.006
 Sample ID: Sample 6
 Tube: tube #3
 Acquisition Date: 07-Apr-22
 Gated Events: 9951
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 16, 15

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	906	9.10	9.06	4.65	3.00	155.76	101.90
UR	704	7.07	7.04	83.58	60.86	192.00	117.15
LL	5898	59.27	58.98	4.06	3.08	2.06	1.55
LR	2443	24.55	24.43	83.27	63.71	1.57	1.18

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Quadrant Statistics

File: Annexin 02032022.001
 Sample ID: Sample 1
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 02-Mar-22
 Gated Events: 9997
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 16, 15

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	452	4.52	4.52	3.50	2.18	141.52	109.11
UR	371	3.71	3.71	89.10	66.25	117.51	82.96
LL	8840	88.43	88.40	2.94	2.37	1.59	1.35
LR	334	3.34	3.34	143.73	94.98	2.10	1.38

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Quadrant Statistics

File: Annexin 02032022.002
 Sample ID: Sample 2
 Tube: tube #2
 Acquisition Date: 02-Mar-22
 Gated Events: 10000
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 16, 15

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	43	0.43	0.43	9.35	8.06	438.04	312.81
UR	351	3.51	3.51	151.78	104.92	217.71	82.96
LL	697	6.97	6.97	5.85	4.91	3.14	2.61
LR	8909	89.09	89.09	132.17	104.09	2.18	1.58

Quadrant Statistics

File: ANNEXIN 06042022.003
 Sample ID: Sample 3
 Tube: tube #3
 Acquisition Date: 06-Apr-22
 Gated Events: 9968
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 16, 13

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	814	8.17	8.14	4.31	2.57	196.11	120.55
UR	1595	16.00	15.95	163.76	109.67	167.43	101.39
LL	4162	41.75	41.62	7.99	6.71	2.05	1.62
LR	3397	34.08	33.97	135.37	62.28	1.89	1.38

Quadrant Statistics

File: ANNEXIN 06042022.004
 Sample ID: Sample 4
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 06-Apr-22
 Gated Events: 9990
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 16, 13

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 10000
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	610	6.11	6.10	4.91	3.06	181.42	117.03
UR	1563	15.65	15.63	147.21	107.13	152.97	98.71
LL	5578	55.84	55.78	7.03	5.86	1.70	1.41
LR	2239	22.41	22.39	150.22	65.61	1.90	1.36

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Quadrant Statistics

File: annexin 280423.001
 Sample ID: sample 1
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 28-Apr-23
 Gated Events: 2425
 X Parameter: Annexin v fit (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 12

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 2430
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	157	6.47	6.46	2.74	2.02	240.45	72.35
UR	122	5.03	5.02	85.02	52.19	457.14	214.75
LL	2047	84.41	84.24	2.28	1.93	3.07	2.46
LR	99	4.08	4.07	40.60	23.96	3.09	2.18

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Quadrant Statistics

File: annexin 280423.002
 Sample ID: sample 2
 Tube: tube #2
 Acquisition Date: 28-Apr-23
 Gated Events: 2330
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 12

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 2340
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	6	0.26	0.26	7.41	7.06	129.53	68.74
UR	686	29.44	29.32	359.04	262.70	266.75	131.90
LL	121	5.19	5.17	4.37	3.63	3.39	2.71
LR	1517	65.11	64.83	400.02	304.76	1.98	1.49

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Quadrant Statistics

File: annexin 280423.003
 Sample ID: sample 3
 Tube: tube #3
 Acquisition Date: 28-Apr-23
 Gated Events: 2577
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 12

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 2595
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	68	2.64	2.62	4.66	4.24	59.29	28.63
UR	92	3.57	3.55	142.07	59.39	231.03	74.28
LL	2306	89.48	88.86	3.28	3.04	4.89	4.30
LR	111	4.31	4.28	76.74	29.49	6.65	5.27

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Quadrant Statistics

File: annexin 280423.004
 Sample ID: sample 3
 Tube: tube #1
 Acquisition Date: 28-Apr-23
 Gated Events: 2573
 X Parameter: Annexin v fitc (Log)
 Quad Location: 10, 12

Log Data Units: Linear Values
 Patient ID:
 Panel: Annexin V
 Gate: G1
 Total Events: 2625
 Y Parameter: IP (Log)

Quad	Events	% Gated	% Total	X Mean	X Geo Mean	Y Mean	Y Geo Mean
UL	17	0.66	0.65	6.25	5.90	41.58	28.03
UR	287	11.15	10.93	312.00	133.21	288.97	81.91
LL	316	12.28	12.04	6.44	5.84	2.83	2.27
LR	1953	75.90	74.40	72.86	32.21	3.59	2.70